

Does drinking coffee accelerate the development of heart failure?

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Annotation: coffee is the second most consumed drink in the world after water, and it is consumed by healthy and sick people from 7 to 70 years old. One of the ingredients in coffee, cocaine, has been found to have a negative effect on the cardiovascular system in several studies. In order to expand these results, this article covers the research conducted in order to study the effect of coffee on heart failure in elderly people with advanced heart failure. Scientists are still working on coffee's benefits and risks for health. Data also found that drinking coffee a lot was associated with more development of heart failure.

Key words: Coffee, caffeine, heart failure, tachycardia, extrasystoles, diabetes, obesity, dyslipidemia, ischemic heart disease, dilated cardiomyopathy, myocarditis, adult people

THE HEALTH BENEFITS OF COFFEE

It is said above that coffee is a highly popular beverage around the world. As more people are drinking coffee daily, its effects on human health are of interest to many medical fields. Some researches suggest that coffee may be associated with lower

mortality risk. It may also help reduce the risk of type 2 diabetes, obesity, dyslipidemia and cardiovascular diseases. These benefits are gathered from large observational studies. However, just because coffee owns a lot of potential health benefits does not mean everyone should drink it regularly. Drinking coffee a lot accelerates the development of heart failure twice. One of the active, main ingredients in coffee is caffeine, an adenosine receptor antagonist that is known for its stimulant effects of central nervous system. Adenosine plays roles in the heart, such as regulating myocardial oxygen consumption and coronary blood flow. It is also widely used in medicine in the treatment of supraventricular tachycardias. We found in our observations that the blockade of adenosine receptors in the heart by caffeine disrupts the above metabolic processes and increases the symptoms of heart failure. Among our patients over 60 years of age, we distinguished those who consume a lot of coffee, especially those with ischemic heart disease, dilated cardiomyopathy and diffuse myocarditis. Some of them have diabetes and liver diseases. They take standard medications while also drinking coffee regularly. We have recorded our expectations for several months. Our study mainly looked at heart failure's sign and symptoms, heart rhythms, sleep, blood sugar and liver enzymes. Patients included in the experiment were constantly submitted to ecg, blood sugar level and liver enzyme analysis. After 6-7 months, we observed that the symptoms of heart failure almost doubled on the background of drugs, for example, patients complained that shortness of breath began at a distance of 800-1000 meters before consuming a large amount of coffee, but after switching to regular intake, shortness of breath began at a distance of 300-400 meters. It was found that these patients also had palpitations of the heart and symptoms of insomnia. When we summarized the ecg tests, it was found that heart palpitations were mainly due to extrasystoles of the atriums, in some patients premature atrial contraction appeared for the first time due to increased coffee consumption, and in some the number of preexisting ones increased. These conclusions were also confirmed by interventional cardiologists in many investigations of large trials. In addition to above, in many patients, the duration of night sleep was reduced by half to one hour. From the worst observational symptoms, heart failure symptoms almost tripled in patients with heart disease and concomitant liver cirrhosis who drank 3-4 cups of coffee per day.

Study limitations

The study did have limitations. First of all, it is limited to carry out specific complex investigations and the study can not evaluate full risk factors. Second, it only included a small number of participants, all of whom had heart diseases, especially, developed heart failure due to ischemic heart disease, dilated cardiomyopathy and myocarditis. Other doctors also acknowledge that some results could have been from activated SNS caused other things or factors related to the study not being a blinded study.

Researchers were also limited by participant adherence to taking standard medications daily and the study's methods. In our view, the main problem may be that patients do not take their medications on time and regularly.

What does this mean for coffee drinkers who are aged 60+. It's necessary to be cautious when understanding these results. They do not show that coffee is overall dangerous or that people aged 60+ should stop drinking it. These findings suggest that an individualized approach to coffee drinking might be the most appropriate method for determining the effects on health.

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